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Research Article

ALPHA – 1 ANTITRYPSIN AMONG NON-SMOKERS AND SMOKERS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

Dr Meryem Tanveer¹, Dr Farwa Sikandar², Dr Lubna Nawaz³

¹ Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan

² Akhtar Saeed Medical and Dental College, Lahore

³ Hamdard College of Medicine and Dentistry, Hamdard University, Karachi

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the present study is to correlate and compare alpha-1 antitrypsin level in smoker and nonsmoker chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients.

Place and Duration: Between May 2019 and May 2020, a study was conducted on COPD patients who went to the Department of Pulmonary Medicine at Nishtar Hospital Multan.

Material and Methods: A comparative study was carried out in 200 subjects, more than 40 years of age and having chronic obstructive pulmonary disease for more than 1 year with a history of smoking at least 20 cigarettes per day (Group A) and without a history of smoking (Group B). Pulmonary function tests were used to diagnose the disease as per the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) classification. Alpha-1 antitrypsin level was done by turbidimetry method on fully auto analyzer I-Lab 650 (Instrumentation Laboratory, USA) at Clinical Biochemistry Section. Statistical analysis was done by using unpaired t-test and Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Results: Results of present study shows that alpha-1 antitrypsin level was decreased in smoker chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients (150.83±18.853) when compared to nonsmokers (183.97±29.383). There was statistically significant difference in alpha-1 antitrypsin level between the two groups with 'p' value of less than 0.0001. Pearson's correlation test show negative correlation between smoker and non-smoker chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients.

Conclusion: The values of serum alpha-1 antitrypsin levels were more significantly decreased in smokers indicating an important role of smoking in pathogenesis of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Alpha-1 antitrypsin can act as a predictor for future development of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in smokers and in nonsmokers.

Keywords: Alpha-1 antitrypsin, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Forced Expiratory Volume (FEV), Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD)

Corresponding author:

Dr Meryem Tanveer,

Nishtar Medical University and Hospital, Multan

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is defined as a medical condition that is not fully irreversible and is characterized by a restriction of airflow containing emphysema, a condition that is anatomically determined by the destruction and expansion of the alveoli; clinically defined condition with chronic bronchitis, chronic cough and sputum; and small respiratory diseases, which is a narrow state of small bronchi. Chronic restriction of air flow is caused by a mixture of small respiratory diseases (obstructive bronchiolitis) and alveolar destruction (emphysema). In developing countries, exposure to excess smoke and mining pollution in nearby environments can cause disease. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is one of the leading causes of health burden worldwide and is the only leading cause of death. The regional research group on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in 12 Asia-Pacific countries and regions used a malaria prevalence model and estimated an overall prevalence rate of 6.3%, 3.5-6.7%. The median study in Pakistan (until 1995) had an incidence of COPD of 5.0% and 2.7% for men and women, respectively, and 5.0% and 3.2% for men and women in 2006, respectively. The rate of progression of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease can decrease when patients at risk of the disease quit smoking, while lifelong smokers have a 50% chance of developing chronic obstructive pulmonary disease throughout their lives. Cigarette smoke activates macrophages and epithelial cells to release chemotactic agents that remove neutrophils and CD8 cells from circulation. These cells release factors that activate fibroblasts, cause abnormal repair processes and bronchial fibrosis. Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency is associated with a significantly higher risk of developing chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, usually for a third or fourth decade, and is also associated with a risk of developing liver disease, dermatitis, bronchitis, vasculitis and Wegener granulation. Patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are alpha-1 antitrypsin posttranslational lesions, oxidation, smoking components are considered due to exposure to smoking. Reactive types of oxygen and nitrogen, the growth of smokers, the purpose and change of alpha-1 antitrypsin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Between May 2019 and May 2020, a study was conducted on COPD patients who went to the

Department of Pulmonary Medicine at Nishtar Hospital Multan. The study included 100 patients (COPD) smokers (group A) with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and 100 non-smokers (group B).

Inclusions: It includes the age of patients over 40 years of age, both men and women, with prior diagnosis of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) by PFT (Pulmonary Function Test). Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional audit committee. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects.

Exclusion Criteria: Patient has an alternative cause of respiratory disorder, e.g., asthma, lung cancer, sarcoidosis, tuberculosis, pulmonary fibrosis, cancer or has had cancer in the 5 years prior to study entry or has had lung surgery, patient with diabetes mellitus, kidney failure, hypertension, heart disease, liver diseases, hepatocellular carcinoma and cancer bladder, compulsive chewing of tobacco and smoking were excluded. Venous blood was collected from all participants under ordinary vacutite. Fresh serum was separated by centrifugation. The test was performed on a fully automatic ILAB-650 analyzer (Instrumentation Laboratory, USA) at the Biochemistry Laboratory accredited by the National Accredited Board for Testing and Calibration Laboratory in accordance with the guidelines of ISO 15189: 2007. AAT was analyzed with serum against human alpha-1-antitrypsin, which reacts specifically with alpha-1-antitrypsin in the sample to yield an insoluble aggregate which is measured by turbidimetry with commercially available ready-to-use reagent kits. Recorded parameters were compared in both groups.

Statistical analysis: All values are presented as mean $\pm$ SEM. Data were checked for normal distribution using GraphPad InStat (version 3.00, GraphPad software, California, USA). In the data analysis, this parameter was compared in smokers and non-smokers with COPD using the unpaired t-test, and their correlation was tested using the Pearson's correlation test. The Pearson's correlation coefficient test was used to correlate serum AAT levels and predicted FEV1% in smoking and non-smoking patients with COPD. Interpretation was made in accordance with the p value. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:**Table 1: Comparison of serum AAT level between two groups**

Statistics	Serum AAT (mg/dl) [§]	
	Group A (COPD Smoker)	Group B (COPD Non Smoker)
Mean ± SD	150.8±18.8	183.9±29.3
Minimum	116	136
Maximum	229	309
Significance	*** p < 0.0001	

*** p < 0.0001: highly significant difference between two groups by applying unpaired t-test with confidence interval. [§]Reference Interval (90-200 mg/dl)

Table-2: Comparison of FEV 1 % between Group A and Group B

Statistics	FEV 1 % (Normal: ≥80%)	
	Group A (COPD Smoker)	Group B (COPD Non-Smoker)
Mean ± SD	48.84±13.6	77.17±14.7
Minimum	16	32
Maximum	88	96
Significance	*** p < 0.0001	

Unpaired t-test with confidence interval of 95%

Fig 1: Correlation between serum AAT and FEV 1% in Smoker COPD Patients

In this study, we measured serum AAT activity in both groups. Although there was a very significant difference between patients in Groups A and B, the Pearson's correlation coefficient was 0.3370 and 0.5026 (p < 0.0001). (Pictures 1 and 2)

Fig 2: Correlation between serum AAT and FEV 1% in Non – Smoker COPD Patients

In the unpaired t-test analysis, the differences in AAT levels between the two groups were statistically significant at <0.0001 "p".

DISCUSSION:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the leading causes of chronic morbidity and mortality worldwide. Chronic restriction of air flow is caused by a mixture of small respiratory diseases (obstructive bronchiolitis) and parenchymal destruction (emphysema). Globally, COPD is the third most important cause of death and is expected to be the leading cause of loss of 5 "adjusted life annuities" (DAYs) according to the Global Disease Load Study (GBDS). Tobacco use kills more than five million people a year and accounts for 10% of adult deaths worldwide. Smoking is considered a more important causal factor for COPD. Various meta-tests have shown that all smoking cessation pharmacotherapy is twice as likely to be more effective with a withdrawal rate of 25-30% per year than a placebo when drug therapy and behavioral support are combined. Alpha-1-antitrypsin has 394 amino acids and 3 glycosylated side chains coupled to asparagines. The amino acid methionine is present at position 358 and it is susceptible to convert in methionine sulfoxide by oxidants from cigarette smoke, rendering it much less potent inhibitor of neutrophil elastase. AAT level was lower in COPD patients with smoking as compared to COPD patients without smoking. The present study shows the significant difference in serum AAT level between the two groups (p less than 0.0001). This study supports the data of previous studies F. Ogushi et al. 1991, Oliver Senn, Erich W Russi, Christian Schindler et al. 2008 16 and Deore Deepmala et al. 2012. There are, however, some limitations to the current study most notably that, the cost of the parameter is high and the sample size is small. Findings of the present study suggest that serum AAT levels were significantly reduced in smoker's COPD in comparison to nonsmoker COPD patients. Therefore, AAT levels can be taken as a parameter to determine the progress of COPD and it can be used as an important tool in the management of COPD. Moreover, serum AAT and FEV 1% can also be used as a risk factor of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease along with smoking as they have significant correlation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

CONCLUSION:

In summary, serum AAT levels were significantly lower in smoking COPD patients compared to non-smoking COPD patients, and there was a positive correlation between alpha-1-antitrypsin and FEV 1% in smoking and non-smoking COPD patients. Therefore, smoking cessation and correction of alpha-1 antitrypsin levels may be beneficial in COPD patients for better treatment of the disease.

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